

PEDAGOGICAL ETIQUETTE.**Abdullazhonova Shakhnoza Akbarovna**

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Abstract. *The article discusses the general rules of etiquette for a teacher, pedagogical tact, the teacher's manners and her role in the education of the future generation. Communicative competence, purposefully improved in the process of rhetorical education, acts as an important component of the professional competence of graduates of higher education institutions in modern conditions of a dynamically developing society.*

Key words: *pedagogical ethics, pedagogical tact, teacher qualities, culture of behavior, teacher authority, behavior, pedagogical morality.*

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ЭТИКЕТ.

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются общие правила этикета учителя, педагогический такт, манеры учителя и ее роль в воспитании будущего поколения. Коммуникативная компетентность, целенаправленно совершенствуемая в процессе риторического образования, выступает важной составляющей профессиональной компетентности выпускников высших учебных заведений в современных условиях динамично развивающегося общества.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогическая этика, педагогический такт, качества учителя, культура поведения, авторитет учителя, поведение, педагогическая мораль.*

The teacher himself must be what he wants the student to be.

(Vladimir Ivanovich Dal)

One of the foundations of a teacher's professional culture is pedagogical ethics. Ethics expresses a person's value relationship to the surrounding reality. A teacher is a person whose professional field of activity is related to teaching. While performing his duties, he interacts with people. These are colleagues and students. Therefore, it is important for a teacher not only to have knowledge and the ability to transfer it to other people. The teacher must pay attention to other aspects. This is competent and respectful communication, behavior, and appropriate appearance. All these rules together are usually called pedagogical etiquette.

Ethics is the doctrine of morality, its principles, norms, development and part in society; a set of norms of behavior usually applied to any group in society.

V. A. Sukhomlinsky said that a teacher will be an educator only when he masters the subtle instrument of education - ethics, the science of morality. At school, ethics is “the practical education of philosophy».

A teacher is a profession that requires a person to constantly communicate with his students, with his children’s parents, and with his work colleagues. The teacher is also responsible for the children he will educate; The teacher also bears responsibility for himself, for his right to be a teacher. The culture of behavior and communication with children plays an important role in the teaching profession. As we know, a teacher is a model for children; they imitate him in everything. The teacher’s responsibilities include nurturing, both in himself and in children, personality, the formation of character is to treat children and their parents with respect, the desire to establish friendly relationships. Compliance with the rules of pedagogical etiquette creates a favorable psychological climate in the team. For the teaching profession, it is very important to have a good command of speech etiquette. Praise and encouragement are found in all professional activities of a teacher. Every day, teachers use these elements when raising their children. At the same time, it is very important to restrain your emotions, especially negative ones, not to humiliate children, the teacher should not raise his voice at children, you also need to watch your facial expressions, especially if these facial expressions are discontent.

Etiquette plays a significant role in the life of a teacher. Etiquette includes rules of behavior and politeness. The teacher’s goal is to develop in his students moral values, ethical culture and way of life, to instill in children friendliness, respect, politeness, and sensitivity towards the people around them. Etiquette is divided into: speech and non-speech. The teacher uses the speech type in his speech, the ability to communicate correctly and conduct a conversation with others, take part in an argument, and make critical or complimentary remarks. Sukhomlinsky paid great attention to the pedagogical word; he wrote that the art of education includes speaking correctly and addressing directly the human heart.

One of the components of a teacher’s professionalism is the ability to master the rules of speech etiquette, which contains important speech formulas that we constantly use in certain situations.

The second type of etiquette includes: actions and deeds, with the help of which the teacher shows students a respectful attitude. Compliance with pedagogical etiquette helps to implement a personal-oriented approach to education, creates an atmosphere for pedagogical communication between student and teacher, aimed at creating a favorable climate among students, which

contributes to the establishment of the necessary relationships with a group of children, and directly with one child.

Pedagogical etiquette also includes the following:

SPEECH ETIQUETTE OF A TEACHER. A teacher is not only a source of knowledge, but also an example to follow. Therefore, he must pay close attention to the culture of speech with which he carries out his activities and conveys the necessary information to students. During the lesson, the teacher pays attention to the rules of teacher speech etiquette:

Speech tone. The tone is restrained, calm, friendly.

Rate of speech. This indicator depends on the age group of the students: for younger children the pace is slow, for older students a higher speed of pronunciation is allowed.

The power of the voice. Raising your voice is unacceptable for a teacher. At the same time, he speaks loudly so that the students can hear him.

Intonation - to make information easier for listeners to assimilate, it is necessary to express it in a special way: make logical pauses, emphasize certain words.

Correctness - the teacher's speech must comply with all norms accepted in the Russian language. Incorrect pronunciation of words, incorrect construction of sentences, and the presence of filler words are not allowed.

Kindness and respect for the opponent. Speech etiquette does not allow aggressive statements or profanity in relation to a specific person, group of people or situation.

TEACHER DRESS CODE. Not so long ago, teachers were prohibited from wearing fashionable clothes, jewelry, and makeup. It was believed that this distracted students' attention from the lesson. But this is in the past, because it has been established that attention is distracted not by a pleasant appearance and a suit, but by boredom, monotony and uninteresting presentation of information.

It is important to pay attention to other components of the image. This is, for example, perfume. He shouldn't be too intrusive. This is unpleasant for the people around you. Bright makeup and manicure are not allowed.

Of course, this does not mean that a teacher should completely abandon the use of cosmetics. But you need to give preference to natural, discreet shades. When it comes to hairstyles, there are no restrictions. The only thing you need to do is keep your hair clean. It is also undesirable to wear loose long hair, which will interfere during classes.

BUSINESS ETIQUETTE OF A TEACHER. In an established team, over time, they develop their own manners of behavior and communication. But general rules of etiquette are mandatory for all teachers. Such norms include:

Punctuality - the teacher arrives at the workplace on time. Even in advance, 15-20 minutes before the start of the first lesson. This is necessary in order to prepare for the lesson, tidy up the classroom and appearance.

Collectedness and neatness - the teacher's workplace is kept in order, documents are in place. This is necessary so that during the lesson the teacher does not waste time looking for the necessary papers or objects.

Restraint - the teacher's rules of behavior do not allow raising one's voice and demonstrating irritation, regardless of the situation. This applies to both colleagues and students.

Tactfulness - a competent teacher will not reprimand a student or colleague in a loud voice and in the presence of other people. After all, it insults and humiliates the opponent.

Subordination - a professional employee of an educational institution does not allow himself disdainful behavior or familiar communication with colleagues who have less work experience or have only recently become part of this teaching team.

The teacher sets an example for the students. This concerns not only knowledge; the child, looking at the teacher, masters the norms and rules accepted in society. And over time, he begins to copy the teacher's behavior. Therefore, it is very important that the teacher observes official etiquette. This applies not only to communication within an educational institution and professional activities, but also to behavior in an informal setting. The most important thing for a teacher is authority, his position in the eyes of colleagues, the administration of the educational institution, students of a given age category, parents of students.

The authority of a teacher is a special professional position that determines the influence on students, giving the right to make decisions, express evaluation, and give advice. The true authority of a teacher-educator is based not on official and age privileges, but on high personal and professional qualities: a democratic style of cooperation with students, the ability to open communication, his desire for constant improvement, erudition, competence, fairness and kindness, general culture, etc. True authority is the attitude of students toward the teacher that encourages students to be the teacher's junior companions. An important role is played by the high level of professional competence of the teacher, deep intelligence, and personal civic position. Pedagogical morality gives the main requirements to the teacher: he must be educated, first of all himself. This is the meaning of pedagogical morality. An individual, whether he likes it or not, is obliged to welcome and support the rules adopted by people.

I will draw a conclusion about the above. Etiquette of a teacher plays a huge role in the life of the growing generation, an individual, and a subject of pedagogical activity. This is a

phenomenon that has a clear structure, dependent on the conditions of social development, associated with the aesthetic, moral, political views of society.

As A.P. wrote Chekhov: "Everything in a person should be beautiful: face, clothes, soul, and thoughts." Indeed, all this undoubtedly influences every student, because a teacher for a student is an idol and an example to follow.

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